

IMPORTANCE-PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF A RESTAURANT MOBILE BOOKING AND RESERVATION APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined issues with performance and ongoing user dissatisfaction in the OpenTable application, a well-known restaurant booking and reservation platform in the Philippines. Researchers use the Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) model to assess OpenTable's importance and performance. Researchers also use Gummesson's 4Q-Quality Model to improve the analysis structure. Researchers gathered comprehensive data by distributing a structured survey questionnaire to 120 individuals who use OpenTable. Ethical considerations guide researchers' investigation at every step. The researchers showed their commitment to methodological and ethical standards by thoroughly outlining the research's design, sampling approach, data gathering methods, and interpretation approaches. A Likert scale was used in the survey questionnaire for performance analysis and importance assessment, and it has been validated through a methodical approach, the findings revealed that: The most significant discrepancy between performance and importance can be observed in the product and service quality (0.70), followed by Designed Quality, Relational Quality (0.59), and Outcome Quality (0.56). For the greatest influence on consumer/users' satisfaction, this proposes putting efforts to make improvements in product and service quality, relational quality, and designed quality. OpenTable is recommended to focus on enhancing communication channels, brand identity, and user experience. Management should place a high priority on resource allocation and transparent communication, and feedback is encouraged. It's recommended that features like responsive reservation updates and live chat assistance be included.

Keywords: *Restaurant Mobile Booking and Reservation Application, Importance Performance Analysis, Gummesson 4Q- Quality Model, OpenTable, Designed Quality, Product and Service Quality, Relational Quality, Outcome Quality*

INTRODUCTION

The restaurant sector had been continuously changing to satisfy the demands of a client base that was becoming more tech-savvy and convenience-oriented in an era of fast technology innovation and shifting consumer tastes. Recent studies about service innovation in the service and hospitality industries mainly focused on technology-related innovation. (Helkkula et al., 2018) pointed out that the hospitality industry was relatively strongly focused on innovations in assortment and technology, leaving non-technological innovation largely unobserved. A new era in restaurant access and engagement has been brought about by the widespread use of smartphones and mobile applications. This study aims to investigate how well the OpenTable application performs from the perspective consumers and the importance of a mobile application for restaurant reservations. Considering that the mobile booking app is becoming an essential component of today's modern dining experience.

With a few taps on their smartphones, patrons could then book tables at their preferred restaurants. The days of making reservations over the phone or standing in huge lines were long gone (Buhalis & Law, 2018). Many believed that online reservations represented one of the largest and fastest-growing segments of B2C e-commerce. Planning and obtaining a table with ease had become possible with mobile booking, which frequently provided real-time availability information and prompt confirmation. In addition to helping customers, this ease enabled restaurants to manage seating arrangements more effectively, which raised customer satisfaction.

The growth of mobile applications for restaurants has improved the dining experience even further. These apps offer a variety of services, such as digital menus, personalized suggestions, loyalty programs, and even mobile payment alternatives, in addition to reservation booking. Jiang (2020) informed that since agent-based models allow us to explore user behavior at the micro-level, we build a simulation model to describe individual decision-making and complex interaction between users of mobile applications in social networks.

The decision to focus this investigation on OpenTable had been supported by evidence that pointed to performance problems and persistently poor user experiences in the Philippines. Critical feedback from consumers of OpenTable, a popular restaurant booking, and reservation application, had been posted on websites including Google Maps and Google Search. Consumers had regularly voiced concerns about a number of issues, such as the cost of restaurants, customer service, rating systems, food quality, and service. One specific TripAdvisor review had highlighted the difficulties that OpenTable customers had; it had expressed both high expectations and a deep sense of frustration regarding the length of wait times for meals, which had resulted in a negative

rating for OpenTable. To reduce these issues and enhance OpenTable's standing in the Philippines, several practical recommendations had been made. In the beginning, it had been essential to conduct a comprehensive study specifically designed for OpenTable's Filipino customer base.

According to a study by Gioseff (2019), there are a number of benefits to studying the OpenTable app. The study indicates a need to comprehend user concerns and enhance the overall experience by revealing user unhappiness and performance issues with the app in the Philippines. OpenTable may be able to grow its customer base and improve its reputation by taking care of these problems. As more people install restaurant reservations on their smartphones, the survey also highlights the significance of mobile optimization. Using Gummesson's 4Q-Quality Model and Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA), the study offers a methodical way to assess the app's effectiveness and identify areas that require development.

To outline the purpose and relevance of conducting an Importance- Performance Analysis (IPA) for a mobile application that allows consumers to book and reserve restaurants. To improve the entire customer experience, this analysis attempts to assess the application's efficacy and user satisfaction while pinpointing areas that require improvement.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of:
 - 1.1. Design Quality
 - 1.2. Product and Service Quality
 - 1.3. Relational Quality
 - 1.4. Outcome Quality

2. What is the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of:
 - 1.1. Design Quality
 - 1.2. Product and Service Quality
 - 1.3. Relational Quality
 - 1.4. Outcome Quality

3. How does the OpenTable mobile app have been assessed using the IPA model?

METHODOLOGY

This study assesses restaurant mobile booking and reservation applications employing survey questionnaires as the primary data collection method and descriptive

data. Descriptive research was regarded as an exploration of existing phenomena through the formulation of inquiries. This approach involved comprehending the meanings attributed to people or objects and was applicable in both quantitative and qualitative research contexts, as articulated by McCombes (2019). It aims to understand demographic profiles and perceptions of quality and services. By bridging the gap between theoretical importance and actual performance, the research aims to identify key features that customers value and provides suggestions for enhancing mobile applications.

The target respondents for this study are consumers of the OpenTable application residing in the Philippines, with a sample size of 120 respondents determined through methods outlined by Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, (2022). Utilizing purposive sampling, the researchers ensured the inclusion of individuals who met specific criteria, such as legal age, residence in the Philippines, and with history of using the OpenTable app for restaurant bookings.

Table 2.1 Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-26 years old	48	40.00
27-42 years old	44	36.70
43-58 years old	28	23.30
59 years old and above	0	0
TOTAL	120	100.00

The table illustrates that the age range among the majority of responders is 18–26, with (40.00%), 27–42 (36.70%), and 43–58 (23.30%). The least represented age group consists of those over 59.

Table 2.2 Respondents as to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	61	51.80
Female	59	49.20
TOTAL	120	100.00

The table indicates that 51.80%, or 61, of the participants are men. However, 59, or 49.20%, of the remaining are female. In summary, 61 or 51.80% of respondents as a whole is male, and only 59 or 45.60% are female.

Table 2.3 Respondents as users of the OpenTable Restaurant Mobile Application

OpenTable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	120	100.00
No	0	0
TOTAL	120	100.00

As shown in the table, majority of participants utilize the OpenTable restaurant mobile booking application. This suggested that a large portion of the studied population relied heavily on OpenTable as their platform of choice for making restaurant reservations.

A structured process was followed for data collection process, involving four phases: creating and developing research tools, validating these tools, distributing research instruments, and analyzing the collected data. They developed survey questionnaires, which were divided into three parts: Personal Profile, Assessment of Importance of mobile food ordering application services, and Performance of mobile food ordering application services. The researchers sought permission to conduct the study and provided participants with a formal letter stating the purpose, objectives, and potential benefits. Researchers conducted face-to-face surveys in Okada Manila, targeting respondents who use the OpenTable mobile booking and reservation application. The collected data was then analyzed by a professional statistician, providing insights to enhance the functionality and user experience of the application.

The survey questionnaire served as the primary instrument for data gathering, designed to capture relevant insights aligned with the study's objectives. The researchers conducted a descriptive study using a survey questionnaire to gather data on the importance and performance of a restaurant mobile booking and reservation application. The questionnaire was designed to gather demographic data and personal experiences from participants. The study assessed the importance of mobile application systems using a 5-point Likert scale and assessed the performance of mobile food ordering application services. The Gummesson 4Q model was applied to the OpenTable app, focusing on four key aspects of service quality: design quality, product quality, relational quality, and result quality.

The data gathered from the survey questions will be tallied, recorded, and evaluated by the researchers. To accurately understand the results of the data analysis and how they will contribute to the study's primary objective, the frequency and percentage will be calculated, along with overall results and final rankings of the criteria included in the survey questionnaires.

Weighted Mean - The objective is to add up several scores. It is the average that was determined by giving several individual variables a different amount of weight.

Formula: $WM = \frac{\sum (W1f1+ W2f2...+wnfn)}{n}$

Where:

- WM = weighted mean
- f1 = frequency of first cell
- w1 = weight of first cell
- f2 = frequency of second cell
- w2 = weight of second cell
- n = number of cases

Percentage - To determine the relationships of a portion to a whole in the respondents' profile.

Formula: $P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$

Where:

- P = percentage

F	=	frequency of each category
N	=	total number of respondents
100	=	constant multiplier

Likert Scale -The five (5) Linkert Scale Method was employed as the criterion for the interpretation of the data.

Likert Scale Interpretation for Importance

Range of Mean	Description Level	Initials
5.00-4.20	Extremely Important	EI
4.19-3.40	Very Important	VI
3.39-2.60	Moderately Important	MI
2.59-1.80	Slightly Important	SI
1.79-1.00	Not At All Important	NI

Likert Scale Interpretation for Performance

Range of Mean	Description Level	Initials
5.00-4.20	Far Above Standards	FAS
4.19-3.40	Above Standards	AS
3.39-2.60	Meets Standards	MS
2.59-1.80	Below Standards	BS
1.79-1.00	Far Below Standards	FBS

Cronbach's Alpha - is a metric used to assess a test or survey's internal consistency. It indicates how closely connected all the questions on a questionnaire relate to one another and quantifies the measure's dependability. Greater consistency and reliability are indicated by higher values, which range from 0 to 1.

Formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k - 1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum V_i}{V_t} \right)$$

Where:

α = alpha

k = number of items in the survey

$\sum V_i$ = summation of variance

V_t = variance of the total score (sum of all item scores)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sub problem No. 1 On the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of

Table 1 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Importance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Designed Quality

Designed Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The interface of the app is visually appealing and easy to use.	4.32	Extremely Important	2
2. The app is easy to use and understand	4.38	Extremely Important	1
3. The application offers simple and easy-to-follow usage guidelines of all its features.	4.08	Very Important	4

4. The app has an eye-catching design and keeps the restaurant its serves' brand identity.	4.10	Very Important	5
5. The application is responsive and works nicely on variety of screens and gadgets.	4.23	Extremely Important	3
General Weighted Mean	4.22	Extremely Important	

/ 5.00-4.20 – Extremely Important | 4.19-3.40 – Very Important | 3.39-2.60 – Moderately Important | 2.59-1.80 – Slightly Important | 1.79-1.00 – Not at All Important |

Table 1 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of designed quality. It can be noticed that the indicator which states, “The app is easy to use and understand.” ranked first with a mean of 4.38. It was followed by “The interface of the app is visually appealing and easy to use.” with a mean of 4.32. Next to it were the indicators “The application is responsive and works nicely on a variety of screens and gadgets.” and “The App has an eye-catching design and keeps the restaurant its serves’ brand identity.” with means of 4.23 and 4.10, respectively. Lastly, the indicator states, “The application offers Simple and Easy-to-follow usage guidelines of all its features.” with a mean of 4.08. The respondents agreed that all these indicators were extremely important in terms of the OpenTable booking app’s designed quality.

In general, the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of designed quality by the respondents was Extremely Important, with a general weighted mean of 4.22.

Relative to the findings of Shahzadi & Riaz (2018), who mentioned that restaurant table reservation systems should provide users with tools to manage and organize their restaurant bookings; to enhance the efficiency and convenience of table reservations in restaurants, it is imperative for the reservation system to possess comprehensive visibility effectively and efficiently. Therefore, it is essential that restaurants should designed a mobile application that is eye catching, visually appealing, and easy to use, a well-designed restaurant food mobile application is crucial for maintaining the brand identity of the restaurant it serves. The design quality plays a significant role in creating a first impression on potential customers. It can also help in building trust and loyalty towards the restaurant’s brand or image. In addition, good design will make an app more user friendly, thus improving customer satisfaction and increasing the likelihood of repeat business and a well-designed app will reflect positively on the restaurant and can contribute to the success in the competitive food service industry.

This indicates that the respondents placed significant importance on the design quality of the OpenTable app, suggesting that they value features such as user interface, ease of navigation, visual appeal, and overall user experience provided by the application.

Table 2 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Importance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Product and Service Quality

Product and Service Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Through the app, users can quickly look up and find restaurants according to their interests	4.31	Extremely Important	1
2. The app offers exact up-to-date information, wait times, and restaurant availability	4.30	Extremely Important	2
3. Users of app can easily book, change, or cancel reservations without any difficulty at all	4.28	Extremely Important	3
4. The application makes sure that transactions are secure and provides a wide variety of payment choices.	4.28	Extremely Important	3
5. The app transmits reservation confirmations, updates, and adjustments in an informative and timely manner.	4.28	Extremely Important	3
General Weighted Mean	4.29	Extremely Important	

| 5.00-4.20 – Extremely Important | 4.19-3.40 – Very Important | 3.39-2.60 – Moderately Important | 2.59-1.80 – Slightly Important | 1.79-1.00 – Not at All Important |

Table 2 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality. It can be noticed that the indicators that state, “Through the app, users can quickly look up and find restaurants according to their interests.” ranked first with a mean of 4.31 each. It was followed by “The app offers exact up-to-date information, wait times, and restaurant availability.” with a mean of 4.30. Next to it was the indicator “Users of app can easily book, change, or cancel reservations without any difficulty at all.”, “The application makes sure that transactions

are secure and provides a wide variety of payment choices.”, and “The app transmits reservation confirmations, updates, and adjustments in an informative and timely manner.” with a mean of 4.28 each. The respondents agreed upon all these indicators as extremely important on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality.

In general, the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality by the respondents was Extremely Important, with a general weighted mean of 4.29.

Relative to the findings of Vinaik, Goel, Sahai, & Garg, (2019), who mentioned that mobile food apps have tie-ups with many restaurants and act as a link between restaurants and people, there are many factors that lead to an increase in sales, such as convenience, easy payment methods, variety of food and restaurants, delivery time, customer service, etc. With its unparalleled convenience, consumers can easily browse restaurant menus and place orders using their cellphones. Easy and secure payment choices further improve the user experience, and the variety of food options accommodates a wide range of tastes and preferences. Therefore, when it comes to the ease with which customers may plan, modify, or cancel meals, good products and services in a mobile restaurant application are mostly beneficial to customers. Easy-to-use interfaces encourage loyalty in addition to increasing client satisfaction. Because reservation management is so simple with this software, it stands out in a crowded market and enhances brand perception. Effective operations, informative data, and flexibility all emphasize how important it is to have a simple and rapid reservation process. All things considered, an appealing and functional app guarantees that users will remain interested and creates a strong and long-lasting relationship between patrons and the business.

The respondents placed significant importance on the quality of products and services offered by the OpenTable app, suggesting that they value aspects such as the accuracy of restaurant information, reliability of the reservation system, responsiveness of customer support, and overall satisfaction with the booking process facilitated by the application.

Table 3 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Importance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Relational Quality

Relational Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. In the case of any problems or question, the app offers prompt and friendly customer care	4.08	Very Important	3
2. The application constantly updates and enhance its features in	3.97	Very Important	4

response to comments and recommendations from users.

3. The application protects user privacy and make sure that private data is managed safely	4.36	Extremely Important	1
4. By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.	3.96	Very Important	5
5. Through personalized offers, unique incentives, and loyalty programs, the app expresses gratitude to its users.	4.17	Very Important	2
General Weighted Mean	4.11	Very Important	

| 5.00-4.20 – Extremely Important | 4.19-3.40 – Very Important | 3.39-2.60 – Moderately Important | 2.59-1.80 – Slightly Important | 1.79-1.00 – Not at All Important |

Table 3 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality. It can be noticed that the indicator that states, “The application protects user privacy and make sure that private data is managed safely.” ranked first with a mean of 4.36. It was followed by “Through personalized offers, unique incentives, and loyalty programs, the app expresses gratitude to its users.” with a mean of 4.17. Next to it were the indicators “In the case of any problems or question, the app offers prompt and friendly customer care.” and “The application constantly updates and enhance its features in response to comments and recommendations from users.” with a mean of 4.08 and 3.97 respectively. Lastly was the indicator that states, “By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.” with a mean of 3.96. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as very important on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality.

In general, the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality by the respondents was Very Important, with a general weighted mean of 4.11.

Relative to the findings (Cho, Bonn, & Li, et al., 2018), who mentioned that with benefits like customized suggestions, reward programs, and contactless ordering as just a few of what users can take advantage of, these applications are a popular choice for consumers wishing to simplify their eating experiences. Reviews, ratings, and ideas are

some of the most important aspects of a restaurant food mobile app that help users feel connected to one another and as a community. These components enable users to contribute their dining experiences, tastes, and suggestions, generating an active forum for conversations on food. Building trust between customers and restaurants is another benefit of being able to read and write reviews, in addition to helping with educated decision-making. Furthermore, customers feel understood and appreciated when they receive tailored recommendations based on their behavior, which improves the entire experience. Along with strengthening the bond between the user and the app, this social interaction creates a lively community of food enthusiasts who may bond over common interests and experiences.

With a weighted average of 4.11 across the board, respondents said the OpenTable app was essential in relationship quality. This shows that factors like communication effectiveness, reliability, responsiveness to feedback, and general satisfaction with the interactions and engagement made possible by the application were highly valued by the respondents when it came to their relationship with the OpenTable platform.

Table 4 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Importance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Outcome Quality

Outcome Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Making restaurant bookings using the app saves the user time and effort	4.42	Extremely Important	1
2. The application lessens the possibility of long queues and waiting times at dining establishments	4.30	Extremely Important	2
3. The app makes dining more enjoyable by simplifying easy reservations and guaranteeing a seamless arrival procedure.	4.24	Extremely Important	3
4. The application increases the possibility of repeat customers and helps user feel more satisfied with the dining establishment	4.18	Very Important	5
5. The application promotes a positive image of the brand and	4.21	Extremely Important	4

engagement of restaurants that
make use of it

General Weighted Mean	4.27	Extremely Important
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| 5.00-4.20 – Extremely Important | 4.19-3.40 – Very Important | 3.39-2.60 – Moderately Important | 2.59-1.80 – Slightly Important | 1.79-1.00 – Not at All Important |

Table 4 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality. It can be noticed that the indicator that states, “Making restaurant bookings using the app saves the user time and effort.” ranked first with a mean of 4.42. It was followed by “The application lessens the possibility of long queues and waiting times at dining establishments.” with a mean of 4.30. Next to it were the indicators “The app makes dining more enjoyable by simplifying easy reservations and guaranteeing a seamless arrival procedure.” and “The application promotes a positive image of the brand and engagement of restaurants that make use of it.” with a mean of 4.24 and 4.21 respectively. Lastly was the indicator that states “The application increases the possibility of repeat customers and helps user feel more satisfied with the dining establishment” with a mean of 4.18. The respondents agreed upon all these indicators as extremely important on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality.

In general, the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality by the respondents was Extremely Important, with a general weighted mean of 4.27.

Relative to the findings of Al-Smadi (2022), mobile commerce has emerged as a vital tool for many firms as smartphones continue to evolve and gain popularity. It offers customers accessibility, enabling them to purchase products or services at any time and from anywhere. Therefore, through the promotion of a good and user-friendly experience, the application plays a critical role in improving the restaurant brand image. Customers are left with a lasting impression of a mobile app that is both professionally designed and practical, reflecting the expertise of the restaurant. It functions as a potent marketing tool that enables restaurants to successfully engage customers, emphasize distinctive aspects, and exhibit their offers. Customer satisfaction and loyalty are raised by positive app experiences like simple navigation, speedy order placement, and tailored recommendations.

This suggests that the respondents gave the results of using the OpenTable app a high priority. These results included making reservations successfully, receiving accurate restaurant recommendations, having a positive overall dining experience, and being satisfied with the results the app helped to achieve.

Sub Problem No. 2 On the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of

Table 5 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Performance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Designed Quality

Design Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The Interface of the app is visually appealing and easy to use.	3.78	Above Standards	1.5
2. The app is Easy to use and understand	3.78	Above Standards	1.5
3. The application offers Simple and Easy-to-follow usage guidelines of all its features.	3.42	Above Standards	5
4. The App has an eye-catching design and keeps the restaurant its serves' brand identity.	3.56	Above Standards	4
5. The application is responsive and works nicely on variety of screens and gadgets.	3.63	Above Standards	3
General Weighted Mean	3.63	Above Standards	

/ 5.00-4.20 – Far Above Standards | 4.19-3.40 –Above Standards | 3.39-2.60 –Meets Standards | 2.59-1.80 – Below Standards | 1.79-1.00 –Far Below Standards |

Table 5 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of designed quality. It can be noticed that the indicators that state, “The Interface of the app is visually appealing and easy to use.” and “The app is Easy to use and understand” ranked 1.5 with a mean of 3.78 each. It was followed by “The application is responsive and works nicely on variety of screens and gadgets.” with a mean of 3.63. Next to it was the indicator “The App has an eye-catching design and keeps the restaurant its serves’ brand identity.” with a mean of 3.56. It was followed by the indicator “The application offers Simple and Easy-to-follow usage guidelines of all its features.” with a mean of 3.42. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as above standards on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of designed quality.

In general, the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of design quality by the respondents was Above Standards, with a general weighted mean of 3.63.

This coincides with Shahzadi & Riaz (2018), who mentioned that restaurant table reservation systems should provide users with tools to manage and organize their restaurant bookings. To enhance the efficiency and convenience of table reservations in restaurants, it is imperative for the reservation system to possess comprehensive visibility effectively and efficiently. Giving users of a restaurant food mobile app clear and simple instructions for all tasks has two main goals: it improves user experience and increases customer satisfaction. With the aid of simple and clear instructions, users can easily run the application, ensuring a seamless ordering experience. The app's simplicity and complexity reduction make it more approachable for a wider audience, including less tech-savvy people. This tactic or strategy increases overall convenience and enjoyment of dining, which benefits the restaurant's brand in addition to increasing customer loyalty. To put it simply, ensuring user involvement and ease of use of the app.

This implies that the responders considered the design elements of the program, including the user interface, usability, aesthetic appeal, and overall user experience. According to the evaluation, even though respondents value design quality, there might be some areas where enhancements could be made to further increase user satisfaction.

Table 6 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Performance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Product and Service Quality

Product and Service Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Through the app, users can quickly look up and find restaurants according to their interests	3.56	Above Standards	5
2. The app offers exact up-to-date information, wait times, and restaurant availability	3.58	Above Standards	3
3. Users of app can easily book, change, or cancel reservations without any difficulty at all	3.64	Above Standards	1
4. The application makes sure that transactions are secure and provides a wide variety of payment choices.	3.58	Above Standards	3

5. The app transmits reservation confirmations, updates, and adjustments in an informative and timely manner.	3.58	Above Standards	3
General Weighted Mean	3.59	Above Standards	

| 5.00-4.20 – Far Above Standards | 4.19-3.40 –Above Standards | 3.39-2.60 –Meets Standards | 2.59-1.80 – Below Standards | 1.79-1.00 –Far Below Standards |

Table 6 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality. It can be noticed that the indicator that states, “Users of app can easily book, change, or cancel reservations without any difficulty at all.” ranked first with a mean of 3.64. It was followed by “The app offers exact up-to-date information, wait times, and restaurant availability.”, “The application makes sure that transactions are secure and provides a wide variety of payment choices.” and “The app transmits reservation confirmations, updates, and adjustments in an informative and timely manner.” with a mean of 3.58 each. Lastly, the indicator states, “Through the app, users can quickly look up and find restaurants according to their interests.” with a mean of 3.56. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as above standards on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality.

In general, the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of product and service quality by the respondents was Above Standards, with a general weighted mean of 3.59.

This coincides with Vinaik, Goel, Sahai, & Garg, (2019), who mentioned that mobile food apps have tie-ups with many restaurants and act as a link between restaurants and people, there are many factors that lead to an increase in sales, such as convenience, easy payment methods, variety of food and restaurants, delivery time, customer service, etc. With its unparalleled convenience, consumers can easily browse restaurant menus and place orders using their cellphones. Easy and secure payment choices further improve the user experience, and the variety of food options accommodates a wide range of tastes and preferences. Therefore, the timely and informative distribution of reservation confirmations, revisions, and alterations inside a restaurant mobile app is essential to a smooth and satisfying client experience. Notifying patrons or customers about their reservations helps manage expectations and reduces the chance of misunderstandings in the fast-paced restaurant industry, where schedules are subject to last-minute modifications. Good communication through the app fosters professionalism and dependability, which raises customer satisfaction and confidence.

This suggests that while product and service quality are considered important by the respondents, they may not be as highly prioritized as other aspects of the app's performance. This rating indicates that there may be areas where improvements could

be made to enhance the quality of products and services offered by the OpenTable app to better meet the users' expectations.

Table 7 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Performance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Relational Quality

Relational Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. In the case of any problems or question, the app offers prompt and friendly customer care	3.35	Meets Standards	5
2. The application constantly updates and enhance its features in response to comments and recommendations from users.	3.41	Above Standards	4
3. The application protects user privacy and make sure that private data is managed safely	3.71	Above Standards	1
4. By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.	3.58	Above Standards	2
5. By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.	3.54	Above Standards	3
General Weighted Mean	3.52	Above Standards	

| 5.00-4.20 – Far Above Standards | 4.19-3.40 –Above Standards | 3.39-2.60 –Meets Standards | 2.59-1.80 – Below Standards | 1.79-1.00 –Far Below Standards |

Table 7 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality. It can be noticed that the indicator that states, “The application protects user privacy and make sure that private data is managed safely.” ranked first with a mean of 3.71. It was followed by the indicators “By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.” and “By providing features like reviews, ratings and suggestions, the app helps user feel more connected to one another.” with a mean of 3.58 and 3.54 respectively. Next to these was “The application constantly updates and

enhance its features in response to comments and recommendations from users.” With a mean of 3.41. These indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as Above Standards on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality. Lastly was the indicator that states, “In the case of any problems or question, the app offers prompt and friendly customer care.” with a mean of 3.35. These indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as Meets Standards on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality.

In general, the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of relational quality by the respondents was Above Standards, with a general weighted mean of 3.52.

This coincides with Relative to the findings (Cho, Bonn, & Li, et al., 2018), who mentioned that with benefits like customized suggestions, reward programs, and contactless ordering as just a few of what users can take advantage of, these applications are a popular choice for consumers wishing to simplify their eating experiences. Reviews, ratings, and ideas are some of the most important aspects of a restaurant food mobile app that help users feel connected to one another and as a community. Quick and friendly customer service is essential for a mobile application that provides restaurant-quality food. Reactive customer service becomes an essential lifesaver for anyone with questions or concerns. A quick and friendly resolution not only fixes problems efficiently but also enhances user experience overall and boosts customer loyalty. This kind of support is crucial for maintaining app users' confidence and satisfaction since it shows a commitment to their needs and concerns. Furthermore, it strengthens the app's reputation by demonstrating that it is a trustworthy and customer-focused meal ordering platform, which eventually increases customer confidence and encourages repeat business.

This suggests that while relational quality, such as communication effectiveness, trustworthiness, and responsiveness to feedback, is considered important by the respondents, it may not be as highly prioritized as other aspects of the app's performance. This rating indicates that there may be room for improvement in enhancing the relational aspects of the OpenTable app to better meet users' expectations.

Table 8 Assessment of the Respondents on the Level of Performance of the OpenTable Booking App in terms of Outcome Quality

Outcome Quality	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Making restaurant bookings using the app saves the user time and effort	3.73	Above Standards	2.5
2. The application lessens the possibility of long queues and	3.75	Above Standards	1

waiting times at dining establishments

3. The app makes dining more enjoyable by simplifying easy reservations and guaranteeing a seamless arrival procedure.	3.62	Above Standards	5
4. The application increases the possibility of repeat customers and helps user feel more satisfied with the dining establishment	3.72	Above Standards	4
5. The application promotes a positive image of the brand and engagement of restaurants that make use of it	3.73	Above Standards	2.5
General Weighted Mean	3.71	Above Standards	

/ 5.00-4.20 – Far Above Standards / 4.19-3.40 –Above Standards / 3.39-2.60 –Meets Standards / 2.59-1.80 – Below Standards / 1.79-1.00 –Far Below Standards |

Table 8 presents the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality. It can be noticed that the indicator that states, “The application lessens the possibility of long queues and waiting times at dining establishments” ranked first with a mean of 3.75. It was followed by the indicators “Making restaurant bookings using the app saves the user time and effort.” and “The application promotes a positive image of the brand and engagement of restaurants that make use of it” with a mean of 3.73 each. Next to these was “The application increases the possibility of repeat customers and helps user feel more satisfied with the dining establishment” with a mean of 3.72. Lastly was the indicator that states, “The app makes dining more enjoyable by simplifying easy reservations and guaranteeing a seamless arrival procedure.” with a mean of 3.62. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents as above standards on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality.

In general, the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of outcome quality by the respondents was Above Standards with a general weighted mean of 3.71.

This coincides with Al-Smadi (2022), who mentioned that mobile commerce has emerged as a vital tool for many firms as smartphones continue to evolve and gain popularity. It offers customers accessibility, enabling them to purchase products or services at any time and from anywhere. The food mobile app for a restaurant is essential

since it may enhance the entire dining experience by simplifying reservations and ensuring a seamless arrival process. Using the app, which streamlines the booking process and provides an intuitive reservation management interface, customers may save time and effort. A more enjoyable dining experience is also achieved by guaranteeing a seamless arrival process, maybe with the aid of computerized check-ins or designated waiting areas. This efficiency not only makes the restaurant more convenient for patrons, but it also conveys the image of a professional business that puts patron satisfaction first., Finally the app's capacity to expedite reservations and improve the arrival process significantly increases customers' enjoyment of their dining experience.

It appears from this that the respondents gave great weight to the results of using the OpenTable app, including successful reservation bookings, the precision of restaurant recommendations, overall dining experiences, and satisfaction with the results made possible by the app.

Sub Problem No. 3 On the OpenTable mobile application assessment using the Importance-Performance Analysis model

Table 9 Importance – Performance Model of OpenTable Booking App

	OpenTable Booking App	
	Importance	Performance
Designed Quality	4.22	3.63
Product Quality & Service Quality	4.29	3.59
Relational Quality	4.11	3.52
Outcome Quality	4.27	3.71

| 5.00-4.20 – Extremely Important | 4.19-3.40 – Very Important | 3.39-2.60 – Moderately Important | 2.59-1.80 – Slightly Important | 1.79-1.00 – Not at All Important |

| 5.00-4.20 – Far Above Standards | 4.19-3.40 –Above Standards | 3.39-2.60 –Meets Standards | 2.59-1.80 – Below Standards | 1.79-1.00 –Far Below Standards |

Table 9 shows the importance – performance model of OpenTable booking app. It can be noticed that the respondents assessed the designed quality in importance at 4.22 and performance of 3.63. In product and service quality, respondents assessed the importance of 4.29 and performance of 3.59. Respondents assessed the importance of 4.11 and performance of 3.52 in relational quality. Lastly, the outcome quality, the respondents assessed the importance of 4.27 and performance of 3.71.

The most significant discrepancy between performance and importance can be observed in the product and service quality (0.70), followed by Designed Quality, Relational Quality (0.59), and Outcome Quality (0.56). For the greatest influence on

consumer/users' satisfaction, this proposes putting efforts to make improvements in product and service quality, relational quality, and designed quality.

The data provides insightful information on how users evaluate the OpenTable application in terms of product and service quality. This performance is rated as "somewhat satisfied" on average, with a weighted mean of 3.59 (above standard), however certain areas need more work. Participants highlight the security aspects, timely communication, and convenience of handling reservations as strengths in their core functionalities. Personalized recommendations or further search customization could be beneficial in the area of restaurant discovery based on interest, which received a bit of a lower rating. Research by Adomavicius et al., (2005) suggested that personalization in recommender systems led to increased user satisfaction and loyalty. OpenTable could leverage user data such as past reservations and dietary preferences to suggest relevant restaurants, creating a more engaging experience. While studies by Zhang et al., (2018) demonstrated that well-designed search filters could significantly improve decision-making processes. By offering filters based on cuisine, ambiance, price range, and accessibility, OpenTable could empower users to find the perfect dining experience. Adomavicius et al., (2005) found that personalization increased user satisfaction. By implementing personalization features, OpenTable could address user feedback and improve satisfaction. It is possible to put user feedback into practice by looking into enhancements like individualized recommendations or better search filters. Zhang et al., (2018) showed that well-designed search filters improve decision-making. Advanced search filters on OpenTable can empower users to make informed choices, leading to a better overall experience. Furthermore, feedback from consumers is required to make sure that improvements properly solve issues found and improve the restaurant finding experience. OpenTable can maintain its position as a leader in restaurant reservations by taking care of these issues.

According to the data, respondents have a favorable opinion of OpenTable's design quality, giving it an overall performance rating of 3.63 (above standard). This suggests that most participants believe the app is easy to use, aesthetically pleasing, and responsive on various devices. The "somewhat satisfied" rating for OpenTable's design indicates that users are generally happy with it. But there's still area for development, especially when it comes to offering simple, understandable instructions on how to use the application. Nielsen (1994) emphasizes the importance of user-centered design principles, which state that clear instructions are essential for a positive user experience. Ambiguous instructions can cause user frustration and prevent task completion. Nielsen (1994) advocated for clear instructions, which can significantly improve the user experience by reducing confusion and frustration. Users can more easily navigate the app and use all of its features. Simple instructions can improve accessibility for users with varying levels of technical knowledge. This is consistent with the core principles of inclusive design, ensuring that everyone can easily use the app. By examining user feedback, specific areas that require clarification in terms of instructions or functionalities may be identified, and graphical elements can be made simpler. Instructions and guidelines should be generated and made available within the app to improve the user experience and enable users to make the most of all the features. By taking care of these

issues, OpenTable can continue providing a visually appealing and useful app while guaranteeing a user-friendly interface that accommodates users with different levels of technical expertise.

OpenTable's initiatives to establish and maintain positive relationships with its users are seen positively by the participants based on the data. With an overall performance rating of 3.52 (above standard), consumers clearly appreciate the app's attention to user connection, data protection, and feedback responsiveness. Still, there are certain areas that could be used better. The fact that OpenTable customers give the app a "somewhat satisfied" in relational quality. Consumers appreciate data privacy policies, which shows that they have faith in the platform. They also recognize that the app makes an attempt to connect users by offering features like recommendations and reviews. Users also value OpenTable's ability to promptly update features in response to their comments. The lowest ranking went to customer service, indicating that there is a need for improvement in terms of interaction, response times, and efficacy in resolving issues. Research by Reichheld (2003) on Net Promoter Score (NPS) demonstrates the critical role of customer service in building loyalty and advocacy. When customers feel valued and their issues are resolved promptly and efficiently, they are more likely to become loyal brand promoters OpenTable can transform satisfied users into brand advocates who recommend the app to others by effectively resolving customer issues (Reichheld, 2003). By taking into consideration these issues, OpenTable can strengthen its bonds with customers, encouraging loyalty and delivering an experience that is more impressive.

Lastly, with an overall performance rating of 3.71 (above standard), the data indicates ideal customer satisfaction with OpenTable's ability to deliver favorable results. Given that it can shorten wait times, save users' time and effort, and improve restaurants' reputations, the app is highly appreciated. Users also like that the app making reservations easier and guarantees a seamless arrival experience, which promotes repeat patronage and increases satisfaction among users. This can involve finding out about user perspectives on managing wait times, communicating about reservations, and how the app can enhance the dining experience in ways other than just simplifying reservations and arrival. Research by McLean et al., (2017) highlights the importance of a holistic dining experience. While reservation ease is crucial, factors like wait times and interpersonal interaction also significantly impact customer satisfaction. OpenTable can explore ways its app can go beyond reservations to elevate the overall dining experience (McLean et al., 2017). This could involve features facilitating pre-ordering, dietary preference communication, or personalized recommendations. OpenTable can utilize these findings to better understand how to work with restaurants to enhance wait times and interpersonal interaction, while also keeping an eye on how the app can make dining experiences more enjoyable for customers.

Through the use of the Importance-Performance Analysis model (IPA), the mobile application for restaurant booking and reservations meets user expectations and increases consumer satisfaction. In this analysis, the effectiveness of the application in

providing various features and functionalities is assessed by the level at which users value those features and functionalities.

Developers and managers can enhance customer satisfaction by pinpointing areas of high importance but low performance, enabling them to prioritize improvements effectively. Identifying features that customers find important, like an easy-to-use interface, a quick reservation process, real-time updates, and smooth arrival procedures is crucial for mobile apps that make restaurant reservations. When this strategy is applied effectively, it helps to match user expectations with app development and enhancement activities, which guarantees a satisfying dining experience for customers and optimizes the app's usefulness for enterprises.

Conclusions

1. On the assessment of the respondents on the level of importance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of:

This study looked into how users felt about the quality of the OpenTable booking app. There was an apparent agreement among users who gave the app top ratings in every variable. With a grand mean of 4.22, it was determined that designed quality, which includes aspects like user interface and simplicity of use was important. Similar to functionality, service reliability, and product quality, these factors were rated as extremely important with a grand mean of 4.29. Although the grand mean of relational quality indicated little discrepancies in importance among particular features, it was nevertheless rated extremely important, indicating that users place a high value on their interactions with the application. In addition, outcome quality which emphasizes favorable results like bookings and a seamless dining experience was given the highest rating with a grand mean of 4.27, suggesting that users place a high value on it. All things considered; this investigation focuses on the importance of every quality level in the OpenTable app.

2. On the assessment of the respondents on the level of performance of the OpenTable booking app in terms of:

The respondents assessed the OpenTable booking app's performance in terms of design quality in Table 4.5. Notably, performance was marginally lower for indicators including responsiveness, visual appeal, and ease of use, despite their high importance. Table 4.6 presents the respondents' evaluation of the quality of the products and services. They viewed factors like secure transactions and convenience of booking to be extremely important, but their performance did not meet their expectations entirely. Table 4.7 focuses on relational quality and emphasizes the value of privacy protection, whereas factors like timely customer service and regular updates performed a bit lower. Table 4.8 concludes the discussion of outcome quality and highlights the importance of features such as timesaving and satisfaction enhancement, despite slight differences in performance ratings.

3. On the OpenTable mobile application assessment using the Importance-Performance Analysis model:

The OpenTable mobile application's Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) provided a clear image of the critical areas that still require improvement, even if users found the program to be generally functioning averaging "somewhat satisfied" scores.

The analysis found important weaknesses. First, customers were not satisfied with the quality of the products and services. In particular, people long for more advanced search options with personalized suggestions to speed up the process of finding restaurants that suit their unique tastes. Second, relational quality needs to be addressed. Customer service contacts need to be improved in terms of performance, response times, and general user interaction, even though people value data security and responsiveness to feedback. Lastly, there is a way to improve designed quality. Clearer in-app instructions would greatly improve the experience, especially for people who are less proficient with technology, even though users found the app to be generally user-friendly.

These are the areas that OpenTable should focus on improving in order to maintain its dominant position in the market. To further accommodate user preferences, personalization mechanisms and smart search filters should be implemented. Enhancing response times and means of interaction and resolving issues in customer service will improve user satisfaction. Creating compact and comprehensible in-app instruction and user manuals will also greatly improve the user experience, especially for users with different technical ability levels. While keeping the key features of the app and its value for users and restaurants, OpenTable can guarantee a user-friendly and delightful experience for a wide range of consumers by focusing on these areas.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following are the recommendations of the study.

For Technology Developers of Mobile Booking and Reservation Applications:

1. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that OpenTable prioritize enhancing the visual appeal of the app to better reflect the unique brand identities of the restaurants it serves. Graphic designers and branding experts can collaborate to revamp the app's interface and incorporate elements that reflect the distinctive attributes of each restaurant's brand. This could include using restaurant-specific colors, logos, and imagery throughout the app to create a consistent and immersive brand experience for users.
2. To address the challenge of navigation complexity highlighted in the study, it is recommended to work towards simplifying the user experience and providing clearer usage recommendations. The user interface should be simple to use, clear, and intuitive for booking, changing, and canceling reservations. Provide in-app

instruction that walks users through the app's main functions, particularly for new users and when they encounter new features. To accommodate different learning styles, use a combination of text, interactive walkthroughs, and quick video tutorials and provide easy access to these tutorials within the app, for example, by creating a special "Help" area, and decreasing the number of steps involved in making a reservation.

3. Permit users to visually verify their information and grant modifications within a fair amount of time. This entails making use of recognizable design indicators, concise labeling, compact content, and orderly layouts. Customers should have no trouble making reservations and finding what they're looking for promptly. Also, regularly test the software to reduce bugs and issues, and provide timely updates to address any issues that arise. Lastly, provides features like the ability to edit booking details, manage waitlists, and manage existing reservations to improve the customer experience.
4. Use automated notifications through email, call, or SMS alerts to keep users informed about their reservations, table availability, cancellations, changes, and confirmations to ensure prompt and transparent communication. Provide immediate notice through email regarding wait times, modifications to reservations, or unforeseen circumstances. Investigate "virtual queuing" options that let users check in from a distance and get notifications when their tables are ready. By focusing on these areas, OpenTable can improve user satisfaction, increase engagement, and foster loyalty among its user base. Additionally, personalized emails will be generated to users with recommendations for new restaurants to try based on their past dining history.
5. Enhancing customer care services by establish safe in-app messaging to facilitate direct user-restaurant contact. This enables users to ask inquiries regarding the menu, get information about wait times, and clarify things. Also, provide a range of support channels such as phone, email, and extensive FAQ, and make sure your agents are kind, knowledgeable, and quick to resolve problems. Additionally, implementing community forum where users can share recommendations and engage with each other can further enhance customer satisfaction. This enables continuous improvement and promptly addresses user needs. Regularly reviewing and acting on feedback demonstrates a commitment to enhancing functionality and meeting user expectations.
6. Install strong safety measures to protect user data and financial information. When a user appears to make a payment, apply secure payment gateways, and always display security identification. Offer a range of payment methods, including trendy e-wallets and multiple banks, and indicate authorized options while a reservation is being made. Have a transparent and easily readable privacy policy that describes how data is collected, used, and shared (if relevant) to keep users' trust. Give users the power to control their settings, access information, and ask for the

erasure of data when they so want, and update the Privacy Policy often to consider any modifications.

7. Use responsive design concepts to ensure the application adjusts to various screen sizes and resolutions on PCs, tablets, and smartphones without any problems. This gets rid of annoyances and discrepancies from the user's gadget. Adjust the button sizes, text legibility, and general arrangement to perfection for every type of gadget.
8. Improve the search algorithm, refine filter options, and implement features such as predictive search to streamline the process and provide a variety of filtering choices according to pricing, cuisine, and even dietary requirements.

For Restaurant owners:

1. Collaborate with OpenTable application to provide special offers or promotions that can be customized to the tastes of the user. Incorporate online menus to help customers make more informed choices and use partnerships with local publications or food critics to curate restaurant suggestions.
2. Restaurants should collaborate with the OpenTable app to help users discover new dining options and make reservations more efficiently.
3. Restaurants can use the app to directly ease reservation adjustments and provide customized notifications with projected wait times or delays.

For Marketing and Sales Teams:

1. To promote OpenTable, collaborate with renowned chefs or food vlogger influencers to create content promoting the app's impact on restaurant branding and engagement. Target potential new users by using their audience reach to raise knowledge of the features and advantages of the app.
2. Make use of social media sites such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and TikTok. By producing brief advertisements or content, social media sites provide the OpenTable app more chances to gain popularity.

For Consumers:

1. Give OpenTable constructive criticism by being open and honest about your impressions of the app to further improve the application. Please report any problems you run into, make suggestions for enhancements, and give concrete examples of how you would like the program to work better for you. Your input can directly impact future advancements. Additionally, consider connecting OpenTable with loyalty programs to maximize benefits and earn rewards for reservations.

2. Examine how OpenTable and loyalty programs can work together. A lot of restaurants have connectors available. To fully utilize the advantages of both platforms, think about connecting your accounts in order to accrue points or rewards for your reservations.

For Future Researchers:

1. Study the effects of user demographics by dividing performance measures, such as geographical location, age, and dining preferences, based on user feedback. This may highlight differences in consumer wants and expectations, guiding the development of additions or changes that have been tailored to the demands of various user groups.
2. Conduct qualitative research to discover how OpenTable affects users' feelings before, during, and after their meal. This can reveal chances to improve user happiness beyond the app's functional characteristics or psychological distress spots.
3. Assess OpenTable's effectiveness in relation to competing applications for booking restaurants. This can reveal new trends, sector best practices, and possible differentiation points for OpenTable.
4. Conduct research to find out how users decide which restaurants to book. This may include researching variables such as user preferences, restaurant details, internet reviews, and OpenTable's impact on such choices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The conduct of the research will be strongly focused on adhering to a set of ethical criteria and resolving any potential issues that might come up throughout the duration of the research in the future. The research tools to be used in this study will be carefully evaluated and authorized by the researcher's adviser, who is an expert in the subject, to ensure the highest level of ethical consistency. The study will receive permission from advisors and will adhere to strict ethical standards. Informed and willing participants will sign a permission form outlining the study's objectives and commitment to confidentiality as proof of their consent. Data integrity, privacy, and participant rights will all be upheld through the implementation of strict data protection regulations.

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